

Summary of the Würzburg Workshop on 6G Networks: WueWoWAS'25

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Abstract—The Würzburg Workshop on Next-Generation Communication Networks (WueWoWAS'25) took place from October 6-8, 2025. About 45 participants from academia and industry discussed about 6G networks, covering advanced architectures, technologies and concepts that will enable the next generation of connectivity, intelligence and automation across multiple domains. The event was technically co-sponsored by the VDE ITG expert group KT 2 on “Communication Networks and Systems”¹ within the German Information Technology Society (ITG), as well as the special interest group “Communication and Distributed Systems” (KuVS)², which is anchored both in the German Computer Science society (GI) and in the ITG. Industrial sponsorship was provided by EMnify and Infosim, and the supporting projects ORIGAMI³ and SUSTAINET-Advance⁴.

I. TECHNICAL CONTRIBUTIONS AND HIGHLIGHTS

The tradition and intention of the WueWoWAS workshop series is to foster the communication among researchers from industry, universities, and other research institutes. To that end, the program featured technical talks on current research, peer-reviewed from an open call, keynote talks by experts of outstanding repute, and tutorial presentations. The technical sessions covered a wide range of subjects addressing various next-generation network paradigms. Some of these works used artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) for 6G communication networks. This allows intelligent, self-optimizing systems to adapt to complex environments. These innovations are instrumental in facilitating autonomous resource management, achieving ultra-low latency, and enhancing connectivity across diverse applications. The contributions addressed RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) telemetry, AI agents and agentic workflows to tackle misconfiguration in campus networks, or AI assisted intent based network management systems. *Henning Sanneck (Apple)* provided a keynote from the UE perspective on native AI/ML in 6G and especially current efforts in UE mobility, utilizing ML for the air interface and RAN (3GPP release 20), RSRP predictions, as well as predictive mobility in a flexible multi-connectivity and cell-free environment. This included an outlook on the emergence of advanced design patterns that integrate AI-native architectures and semantic communications towards self-evolving, context-aware networks beyond traditional connectivity.

¹<https://www.vde.com/itg-kt2>

²<https://kuvs.de>

Fig. 1. Attendees of the WueWoWAS'25 workshop on 6G networks with technical sponsorship by VDE ITG expert group KT 2 and the GI/ITG KuVS, industrial sponsorship by EMnify and Infosim, and the supporting projects ORIGAMI³ and SUSTAINET-Advance⁴.

From the perspective of verticals, industrial networking drives 6G toward deterministic, AI-enabled communication frameworks that integrate sensing, control, and connectivity to meet the stringent demands of industry applications. *Johannes Riedl (Siemens)* highlighted in his keynote the requirements of industrial networks and verticals in the domain of manufacturing, healthcare or energy networks. The vision is to enable vertical industries to focus on their application and innovation rather than operating the infrastructure, through zero-effort networking and providing connectivity as a service to industries. Zero-effort networking envisions fully autonomous, self-managing systems that eliminate manual configuration and optimization, enabling seamless connectivity and user experience across 6G environments. Key components are intent-based network orchestration using AI and ML, as well as technologies supporting deterministic networking like time-sensitive networking (TSN). The technical sessions included also methods how to improve time synchronization accuracy for 5G links or time-aware shaping in TSN based on Centralized Network Controller (CNC) for dynamic reconfiguration to meet industrial requirements.

³<https://sns-origami.eu/>

⁴<https://sustainet.de/>

Several contributions addressed O-RAN (Open Radio Access Network), which is an open, interoperable architecture for mobile networks that disaggregates traditional RAN components and introduces open interfaces. It may enable flexible, intelligent, and interoperable network architectures that support AI-native functions and efficient deployment of services such as network slicing, edge intelligence, and adaptive radio optimization. Approaches were presented how to optimize the RAN lifecycle management for industrial 5G using NetDevOps-driven deployment framework for industrial open RAN that replaces complex orchestration with infrastructure as code (IaC) and Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD). Also mobility was discussed in that context and, in particular, a UE-centric handover mechanism tailored for industrial Open RAN deployments that proactively initiates transitions before connectivity degrades below acceptable levels. *Stanislav Lange (NTNU)* provided a tutorial to the attendees on Open RAN and 5G campus networks setup. In particular, key building blocks for setting up a private 5G testbed using Software-Defined Radios (SDRs), open source software components such as OpenAirInterface and srsRAN, and off-the-shelf modems / phones.

Several technical contributions emphasized the evaluation of network performance and quality of service (QoS), but also reliability and resilience, as well as power consumption and sustainability. One study presented a detailed assessment of power consumption and energy efficiency of fiber optic SFP modules as well as metrics to quantify energy efficiency in the context of communication networks. *Frank Loh (University of Würzburg)* gave a tutorial on energy measurements, metrics, and models, with a focus on methods for measuring power consumption in communication networks as well as software-based approaches for approximating the power consumption. Energy efficiency metrics from literature were revisited and pitfalls in their usage were discussed. *Carmen Mas Machuca (Universität der Bundeswehr München)* gave a tutorial on resilience metrics and models for communication networks. A variety of resilience metrics and their computation were discussed, providing meaningful guide for research. The minimum flow cut was discussed in the context of resilience modeling, which measures the smallest set of links or nodes whose removal most severely reduces network flow, making it a key indicator of a system's structural and functional robustness. In the technical sessions, flow availabilities were also analyzed by investigating the correlation between minimal cut sets and flow availabilities. However, balancing sustainability, performance and resilience may introduce a fundamental research challenge. One work considered to design photovoltaic-powered server clusters that operate energy-efficiently with minimal environmental impact while maintaining high performance and resilience under varying workloads and fault conditions. Novel approaches addressed island-ready 6G communication, which envisions resilient, self-sustaining networks capable of maintaining connectivity in isolated or infrastructure-limited environments. To this end, the conceptual model of island connectivity was introduced and results on the users' perspectives presented, which triggered discussions on the design implications for operators, developers, and authorities.

The next highlight was the keynote by *Rastin Pries (Nokia)* on spatial computing in the 6G era. The paradigm of spatial computing refers to technologies and concepts that merge the physical world, the digital world, and the human world. Spatial computing represents a paradigm shift in the manner in which human-computer interactions function, moving towards a more bidirectional model. The device serves not only to augment the user's perception of the world with digital information, but also to provide contextual information to the application. This contextual information can include the user's current physical context and gestures, thereby facilitating more natural interactions with the computing application. It is key to comprehend and engage with three-dimensional space, thereby empowering devices to perceive, map, and respond to the environment. This requires advanced sensing, AI-driven data fusion, and low-latency processing to ensure accurate spatial awareness and seamless synchronization between physical and digital environments for real-time digital twins.

The paradigm of quantum communication was introduced by *Karim Elsayed (Leibniz University Hannover)* in a tutorial. Quantum communication forms the foundation for connecting multiple quantum computers to collaboratively solve complex problems. This approach is driven by the difficulty of sustaining large-scale quantum systems. Unlike classical communication, quantum communication is governed by unique quantum properties, requiring fundamentally new concepts and techniques. To this end, the tutorial introduced the core principles of quantum communication, its unique features, and evaluated the performance of the communication system for different approaches in light of these distinctive features.

A key part of the WueWoWAS workshops is the integration of PhD students into the research community and the exchange between academia and industry. This included the technical mentorship through focused tutorials, but also a dedication *speedmentoring session*. In that speedmentoring event, PhD students were connected with leading experts from academia and industry for short, targeted discussions on research topics, emerging trends, and career development. The discussions continued at the social event in a traditional Würzburg restaurant, which served Bavarian cuisine and specialties like Franconian wine soup in a relaxed atmosphere.

To integrate PhD students also in the academic review process, experienced PhD students were invited to participate as reviewers. A *reviewer reflection forum session* was part of the WueWoWAS'25 event in order to foster transparency and understanding of community standards from the perspective of reviewers and authors: what reviewers and authors value in the review process; what should be addressed in a submission and in a review; what practices to avoid; what is the hardest part as reviewer. Such community-oriented efforts are essential and highly relevant, as they cultivate an inclusive and supportive research ecosystem where early-career scientists can learn, connect, and contribute meaningfully. This was followed by open discussions on the focus theme for the next WueWoWAS workshop in 2026. Integrating PhD students into mentorship, peer reviews, and open discussions is key for their academic maturation and for strengthening the sense of belonging within the community and the vitality of the research community.

II. KEYNOTE TALKS FROM INDUSTRY

The program included three keynote talks by well known experts from industry players, that are also actively participating in the VDE ITG expert group KT 2 “Communication Networks and Systems”. This expert group works on the key technologies and methods required for the development of future communication networks and systems. The specialist group is made up of experts from ICT companies and universities in order to promote an intensive exchange between industry and science. The WueWoWAS workshop provides a platform for this exchange. The goal is to showcase current industrial research efforts and align participants’ research with practical insights. The WueWoWAS’25 organizers are delighted to receive strong technical support from industry partners, which added valuable practical insights to the event. This collaboration was not only technically enriching but also reinforced the spirit of community. A brief summary of the contents as well as the background of the speakers is given in the following. The keynote speakers were also participating as mentors in the speedmentoring session.

Henning Sanneck (Apple): “Towards Native AI/ML in 6G: a UE perspective”

Background: Henning Sanneck is Research Manager, Wireless Technology at Apple, Munich, Germany. After he received his Dr.-Ing. (PhD) degree in Electrical Engineering from the Technical University of Berlin in 2000, Henning joined Siemens – Mobile Networks, becoming an Innovation Project Manager in 2003. In 2007, at the formation of Nokia Siemens Networks, he started to lead a line team, creating Self Organizing Networks (SON) concepts and demos, and later applying Analytics and Machine Learning technologies to this area using both network data- and simulation-based approaches. From 2016 to 2022 Henning acted as Nokia Department Head for 5G / 6G Network Automation Research, providing vision, strategy, concepts and IPR to support 3GPP, ORAN and ETSI standardization efforts. In 2023 Henning was Chief Architect AI/ML in Nokia Standards. Henning has 100 publications and 50 patents granted or published. He was co-editor of the book "LTE Self-Organizing Networks" (2011) and co-author of the book "Towards Cognitive Autonomous Networks" (2020).

Keynote and discussions: The focus of the keynote was the UE perspective on native AI/ML in 6G and especially current efforts in UE mobility. 3GPP Release 20 include enhancements around AI/ML integration in the air interface and mobility. It focuses on embedding learning-based mechanisms for channel estimation, beam management, and resource optimization, in order to enable adaptive, data-driven 6G radio systems. Predictive mobility refers to the use of AI and data-driven models to anticipate the future movement or connectivity needs of mobile users or devices. By analyzing contextual information such as location history, velocity, network conditions, and application requirements, predictive mobility enables the network to proactively manage handovers, resource allocation, and connectivity paths. In the future, cell-free and multi-connectivity architectures may enable seamless, reliable

communication by allowing users to connect simultaneously to multiple distributed access points without traditional cell boundaries. In that sense, predictive mobility in a flexible, multi-connectivity and cell-free environment leverages AI-driven context awareness to anticipate user movement and seamlessly orchestrate link transitions for uninterrupted, high-quality service. An important aspect of future evolutions of 6G networks is the emergence of advanced design patterns. These patterns integrate AI-native architectures, semantic communications, and intelligent reconfigurability to go beyond traditional connectivity towards self-evolving, context-aware networks.

Johannes Riedl (Siemens AG): “Industrial Networking in 6G”

Background: Johannes Riedl studied mathematics and physics at the LMU in Munich and finalized his PhD in mathematics at the Technical University in Munich in 2001. Afterwards he joined Siemens Information and Communication Networks as R&D engineer. There he was responsible for the development of innovative carrier network design concepts focusing on IP/Ethernet technologies. Joining Siemens Corporate Technology in July 2005, he was leading between 2006 and 2022 the Research Group ‘Industrial Networks’ focusing on wired communication network technologies for industrial networks in all Siemens business areas. Since September 2022 he is heading the Research Group "Industrial Networks & Wireless" which consists of three portfolio elements "Deterministic Communication & Edge Networks", "5G/6G/Wireless" and "Network Intelligence & Localization".

Keynote and discussions: The keynote first introduced the requirements of industrial networks and verticals. Verticals refer to industry-specific domains such as manufacturing, healthcare, transportation, or energy that apply advanced communication technologies to meet their unique operational needs. The presented vision for industrial networking is to enable vertical industries to focus on their application and innovation rather than operating and managing the underlying physical networking and compute infrastructure. This is expressed by the term connectivity-as-a-service to industry with tailored, on-demand network solutions that support diverse industrial applications with guaranteed performance, reliability, and scalability. The concept of zero-effort networking involves the implementation of fully autonomous, self-managing systems that eliminate the need for manual configuration and optimization. Intent-based network orchestration enables intelligent systems to interpret human intentions and requirements, automatically translating them into real-time network configurations and actions for adaptive, goal-driven connectivity management. This requires advanced technologies like network digital twins but also explainable AI (xAI) to understand AI’s reasoning processes.

Rastin Pries (Nokia): “Spatial Computing in the 6G Era”

Background: Rastin Pries received his master and Ph.D. degrees in computer science from the University of Würzburg, Germany in 2004 and 2010. In 2015, he joined Nokia, Munich, where he is currently working as a Principal Research Lead. He has more than fifteen years of experience in the telecommunication industry. Rastin Pries was the consortium leader

of several national and international research projects such as the German BMFTR lighthouse project 6G-ANNA. He is the author of numerous scientific conference and journal papers as well as patents. His research interests include extended reality, spatial computing, edge computing, and localization and mapping.

Keynote and discussions: The paradigm of spatial computing encompasses technologies and concepts that integrate the physical, digital, and human worlds. It marks a significant shift in human-computer interaction toward a bidirectional model, in which devices not only augment human perception with digital information but also interpret contextual data such as the user's physical environment and gestures. This enables more intuitive and natural interaction with computing systems. Achieving accurate spatial awareness and seamless synchronization between physical and digital environments requires advanced sensing capabilities, AI-driven data fusion, and low-latency processing to support applications such as real-time digital twins and immersive experiences. Spatial computing for industrial applications includes the use of extended reality, edge computing, and precise localization to enhance productivity and reliability in smart factories. The research involves developing edge computing and localization approaches to support spatial awareness and dynamic network reconfiguration in industrial settings. Object recognition and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping are utilized for spatial modeling, and these methods are integrated with mobile networks to enable robust communication and automation.

III. TECHNICAL PROGRAM

The technical sessions featured contributions selected from the open call for papers, with all submissions undergoing a peer-review process. Each accepted paper was presented in a about 20-minute oral session followed by a 10-minute question-and-answer. The following sections include the abstracts of all contributions, organized by session.

Session 1: ML & AI in 6G (Chair: Stefan Geißler)

“From data to decisions: Cross-domain QoS optimization via RIC telemetry and ML” [1] was presented by Suneet Kumar Singh (NTNU, Norway): Achieving optimal Quality of Service (QoS) across Radio Access Network (RAN) and core network domains in B5G and 6G is challenging due to dynamic traffic and stringent performance requirements. Continuous edge network monitoring is essential to quickly identify critical applications and allocate resources efficiently, rather than relying solely on a fixed, core-centric QoS approach. This monitoring can also guide the core network in updating QoS policies based on edge insights. This paper proposes a cross-domain QoS optimization architecture covering both RAN and core network. Our implementation focuses on the RAN, presenting a RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC)-based framework for runtime traffic classification and adaptive Physical Resource Block (PRB) allocation, evaluated on a B5G testbed with open-source RAN (srsRAN, OAI) and Machine Learning (ML)-driven extensible applications (xApps). We also discuss how these findings can support future

core network QoS optimization. All code is released open source to support further research.

“An agentic workflow for the remediation of silent misconfigurations in IaC deployments” [2] was presented by Piotr Zuraniewski (TNO, The Netherlands): Large Language Models (LLMs) have seen widespread adoption in software development pipelines due to their ability to process and generate text adhering to a specific syntax, for example software code or application configuration. Their increasing prevalence is emphasized by their use as software agents, autonomous entities within a development pipeline capable of performing a set of tasks on a given artifact. A confounding factor for their adoption in deployment pipelines, in comparison to development ones, is the potential for silent misconfigurations - conditions where an application appears to be successfully deployed but fails to perform its tasks due to invalid parameters passed to it. This paper evaluates the ReAct model for AI agents in the context of a silent failure in a cloudnative Open5GS deployment. It further explores the effect of modifying the behaviour of the ReAct model and proposes a multi-agent approach that significantly outperforms a single ReAct agent.

“An AI assisted Intent based Network Management System for Open Campus Networks” [3] was presented by Varun Gowtham (Fraunhofer FOKUS, Germany): The evolving trend of dis-aggregated telecommunication networks coupled with emerging access technologies and user applications, has made network management systems to look beyond the traditional policy-based automation. Introduction of autonomy into network management has sparked interest in industry and research community, primarily as an evolutionary step and for the added benefits such as simplicity and lower complexity. This paper focuses on investigating Intent-based Networking (IBN) to encapsulate dedicated AI/ML models into strategically compose-able atomic blocks. The paper investigates the possibility of using IBN framework for addressing use cases such as energy efficiency, resource management and Quality of Service (QoS) optimization.

Session 2: TSN (Chair: Amr Rizk)

“A novel method to improve gPTP based time synchronization accuracy for asymmetric 5G links” [4] was presented by Anas Bin Muslim (University of Applied Sciences Osnabrück, Germany): This paper addresses the issue of Time Synchronization for Time Sensitive Networks (TSN) that include wireless 5G links. Precision Time Protocol (PTP) based time synchronization assumes symmetric Ethernet links over which the devices are synchronized. While the assumption of symmetric links is true for Ethernet networks, it might be violated for 5G networks because of the uplink-downlink latency asymmetry. To address latency asymmetry, PTP provides a constant user configurable asymmetry parameter which can be set before starting the PTP synchronization process. However, the latency asymmetry in 5G networks is not constant due to the radio resource allocation requests and grants required for uplink transmissions. In this paper we introduce a novel concept based on time-stamping of the resource requests and

grants in order to increase the PTP synchronization accuracy in TSN over 5G networks. For the proposed method, Time Translators, as introduced by the IEEE for 5G-TSN integration, are not required. Additionally the presented method also works for 5G devices and networks which do not support System Information Block 9 (SIB9) messages.

“*A modular CNC for time-aware shaping in TSN*” [5] was presented by Felix Meyer (University of Applied Sciences Osnabrueck, Germany): Industrial networks serve a wide range of applications with highly varying Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements. Fulfilling these requirements is extremely challenging for the underlying networks, especially in dynamic environments. As traffic patterns vary across multiple applications during runtime, the overall network load becomes highly dynamic, making QoS enforcement difficult. To address this the Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) standards introduce the Centralized Network Controller (CNC) which can be used for dynamic reconfiguration of the underlying network and traffic shaping to ensure the QoS for all applications. In this work, we present a modular CNC architecture and an initial implementation of a CNC capable of configuring time-aware shaping in TSN bridges via the Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF), to verify compliance with IEEE YANG standardized CNC functionality. We tested the CNC using off-the-shelf TSN bridges, a talker, and a listener.

Session 3: 6G Use Cases (Chair: Stanislav Lange)

“*Extended abstract: User perspective on island-ready 6G communication*” [6] was presented by Leon Janzen (Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany): This is an extended abstract of The User Perspective on Island-Ready 6G Communication: A Survey of Future Smartphone Usage In Crisis-Struck Areas with Local Cellular Connectivity [1], published in the Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems with an honorable mention. It introduces the conceptual model of island connectivity, presents the results of our online survey to understand users’ perspectives on it, and derives design implications for operators, developers, and authorities.

“*Receiving kernel-level insights via eBPF: Can ABR algorithms adapt smarter?*” [7] was presented by Farzad Tashtarian (Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt, Austria): The rapid rise of video streaming services such as Netflix and YouTube has made video delivery the largest driver of global Internet traffic including mobile networks such as 5G or the upcoming 6G network. To maintain playback quality, client devices employ Adaptive Bitrate (ABR) algorithms that adjust video quality based on metrics like available bandwidth and buffer occupancy. However, these algorithms often react slowly to sudden bandwidth fluctuations due to limited visibility into network conditions, leading to stall events that significantly degrade the user’s Quality of Experience (QoE). In this work, we introduce CaBR, a Congestion-aware adaptive BitRate decision module designed to operate on top of existing ABR algorithms. CaBR enhances video streaming performance by leveraging real-time, in-kernel network telemetry collected via the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF). By utilizing

congestion metrics such as queue lengths observed at network switches, CaBR refines the bitrate selection of the underlying ABR algorithms for upcoming segments, enabling faster adaptation to changing network conditions. Our evaluation shows that CaBR significantly reduces the playback stalls and improves QoE by up to 25% compared to state-of-the-art approaches in a congested environment.

“*Delay variance mitigation for distributed UAV swarm navigation in wireless MARL*” [8] was presented by Babak Salamat (Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt, Germany): This document is a work in progress to design autonomous flying for urban air mobility (UAM). UAM envisions a future where swarms of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) operate autonomously in dense urban environments, requiring robust navigation and reliable communication. We consider UAVs as agents, and the latency inherent to their coordination. In this work, we consider the problem of a signal-plus-interference-to-noise ratio (SINR)-aware waypoint selection framework that integrates wireless signal quality into trajectory planning to optimize delay performance between UAVs operating over a network. By formulating cost functions that jointly consider travel distance and SINR, each UAV selects paths to reach a designated destination. We propose to minimize the variance of the delay using both model-driven (SINR-based) and data-driven (delay timestamps) approaches. Our aim is to demonstrate how autonomous UAVs can learn optimal trajectories from noisy observations and adaptively respond to dynamic channel conditions. This work contributes to the development of resilient, low-latency UAM systems by bridging the gap between wireless communications and autonomous navigation. For instance in predictive networking, digital twin preempts latency through simulations and reinforcement learning model training.

S4: Sustainability & Resilience (Chair: Piotr Zurawski)

“*Power consumption and energy efficiency assessment of fiber optic SFP modules*” [9] was presented by Noah Mehling (University of Würzburg, Germany): The growing demand for high-throughput Internet connections has driven the adoption of fiber-optic communications. Combined with the challenges posed by climate change, evaluating the energy efficiency of such networks has gained importance. As numerous deployed devices across all network segments, Network switches are of particular concern. While prior research has largely focused on fixed-port configurations, modern switches often use modular transceivers due to different wavelengths, standards, and deployed connectors. One common standard for this purpose is the small formfactor pluggable (SFP) module. Manufacturers rarely specify the exact power consumption of their modules, requiring users to measure power consumption themselves, to analyze energy efficiency. To address this gap, we present a non-invasive methodology to measure the power consumption of SFP modules in operational switches. This enables isolation of the module’s power consumption from the remaining switch hardware. Using this approach, we evaluate the energy efficiency of different SFP modules in two representative fiber-optic switches.

“Investigating the correlation between minimal cut set and flow availabilities” [10] was presented by Shakthivelu Janardhanan (TU Munich, Germany): A flow is any traffic between a source and a destination. Network availability is defined as the ability of a network to route all flows at a given time instant. A network’s availability depends on the availability of every flow in the network. A flow’s availability expression based on the node and link availabilities is non-linear and can not be used in Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) formulations as constraints. Hence, we propose a new availability estimation based on minimal cutset (MCS). MCSs of a flow are the smallest possible set of components that can cause flow failure. We compare the MCS-based flow availability estimation with the accurate flow availability. The evaluation of several studies on different topologies confirms that there is a high correlation. Therefore, we propose the use of the MCS-based flow availability estimation to build linear MILP constraints to improve network availability.

This paper received the **Best Student Paper Award** at WueWoWAS’25, recognizing both the quality of the submitted contribution and the excellence of the oral presentation delivered by Shakthivelu Janardhanan during the workshop.

Fig. 2. Best student paper award for the work “Investigating the Correlation Between Minimal Cut Set and Flow Availabilities” [10], presented by Shakthivelu Janardhanan. From left to right: Amr Rizk, Tobias Hofffeld, Shakthivelu Janardhanan, Stefan Geißler.

“Balancing sustainability and performability: A Markov model of a photovoltaic-powered server cluster under varying load” by Carina Baur (University of Würzburg, Germany): The increasing demand for reliable communication infrastructure is leading to a significant rise in energy consumption. Concurrently, the need to address challenges posed by climate change underscores the importance of sustainable system design. This introduces a fundamental research challenge for the next decade: balancing sustainability, which focuses on energy efficient operation of systems with little or no environmental impact, with performability, which encompasses both system performance and resilience under varying workloads and fault conditions. These objectives are often in conflict, necessitating a systematic evaluation of the associated trade-

offs. To this end, this paper models a small server cluster with time-dependent computational loads and a photovoltaic energy supply to explore this interplay. Through mathematical Markov models, we provide a methodology to explore how different system configurations influence both sustainability metrics (e.g., energy usage, renewable energy share) and performability (e.g., service availability). While numerical results are beyond the scope of this extended abstract, we discuss potential insights into designing systems that are both resilient and environmentally responsible for the future generation of communication networks.

Session 5: Open RAN (Chair: Simon Raffeck)

“UE-based proactive handover in industrial Open RAN deployment” [12] was presented by Hubert Djuitcheu (Adtran, Germany): Ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) is crucial for ensuring several key use cases in industrial 5G deployments. However, traditional, network-coordinated handover (HO) often introduces long delays and service interruptions, which can disrupt time-sensitive applications. This paper proposes a user equipment (UE)-centric handover mechanism tailored to industrial Open RAN deployment. In this approach, each UE (e.g., a mobile robot) continuously monitors local key performance indicators (KPIs) (reference signal received power (RSRP), reference signal received quality (RSRQ), Signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), etc.) and autonomously triggers a handover before connectivity degrades below acceptable levels. Experimental results demonstrate a reduction in handover delay and improved signal continuity, validating the effectiveness of the proposed method in an industrial environment. The framework is scalable to multiple UEs and cells and adaptable to varying interference conditions, making it suitable for mission-critical industrial applications.

“RAN master: A lightweight deployment and lifecycle management for industrial 5G” [13] was presented by Hubert Djuitcheu (Adtran, Germany): The deployment of industrial open radio access network (RAN) presents unique lifecycle management challenges, particularly in environments where resilience, remote operability, and real-time responsiveness are crucial. In this work, we introduce a new deployment approach (RAN master) that balances performance, automation, simplicity, and minimizes orchestration overhead without compromising system reliability. Rather than relying on complex container orchestration platforms like Kubernetes, we adopt a lightweight model based on Docker Compose. Our methodology is grounded in NetDevOps principles and leverages infrastructure as code to ensure reproducibility and automation. A centralized YAML blueprint defines the network topology and configuration, from which we generate per-cell Docker compose files. These are integrated into a GitLab CI/CD pipeline that handles validation, provisioning, and activation. This approach has been deployed at our Terafactory in Meiningen, where it supports realtime industrial workloads with minimal latency and high availability. The results confirm that selective containerization, combined with declarative automation, offers a scalable and maintainable path for industrial 5G deployments.

IV. TUTORIALS

The four tutorials were given on the last day of WueWoWAS'25. The target audience were PhD students and researchers interested in the topics. Each tutorial was a 90 minute presentation, which are available as part of the WueWoWAS proceedings. A brief abstract of the tutorials as well as the background of the speakers is provided in the following.

Fig. 3. Tutorial speakers with the city of Würzburg in the background. From left to right: Tobias Hofffeld, Carmen Mas-Machuca, Karim Elsayed, Frank Loh, Stanislav Lange.

Karim Elsayed (Leibniz University Hannover): Introduction to Quantum Communication using Computer Science and Performance Evaluation

Background: Karim Elsayed is pursuing his Ph.D. in the Distributed Real-Time Systems group at the Department of Computer Science, Leibniz University Hannover. He obtained his Master's degree in Communication Engineering and Technology from Ulm University. His research interests include the modeling and optimization of communication and networked systems, with a current focus on the performance evaluation and optimization of quantum networks.

Tutorial scope: Quantum communication forms the foundation for connecting multiple quantum computers to collaboratively solve complex problems. This approach is driven by the difficulty of sustaining large-scale quantum systems. Unlike classical communication, quantum communication is governed by unique quantum properties, requiring fundamentally new concepts and techniques. This tutorial explains the core principles of quantum communication, its unique features, and evaluate the performance of the communication system for different approaches in light of these distinctive features.

Slides: The slides of the tutorial [14] are available online: DOI: 10.25972/OPUS-42659.

Frank Loh (University of Würzburg): Energy Measurements, Metrics, Models

Background: Frank Loh received the Ph.D. degree from the University of Würzburg in 2024 for his thesis Monitoring

the Quality of Streaming and Internet of Things Applications. He is currently with the Chair of Communication Networks, University of Würzburg, where he leads the Green Communication Networks Research Group. His current research address a greener way of communication without impacting the user perceived application quality.

Tutorial scope: Methods for measuring power consumption in communication networks as well as software-based approaches for approximating the power consumption were introduced and discussed. Energy efficiency metrics from literature and standardization were revisited to avoid common pitfalls and misinterpretations.

Slides: The slides of the tutorial [15] are available online: DOI: 10.25972/OPUS-42661.

Stanislav Lange (NTNU): Open RAN and 5G Campus Networks Setup and Measurements

Background: Stanislav Lange received his M.Sc. and PhD degrees in Computer Science from University of Würzburg in 2014 and 2018. The topic of the PhD thesis was on the Optimization of Controller Placement and Information Flow in Softwarized Networks. Currently, he is an associate professor at the Department of Information Security and Communication Technology at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim, Norway. His research is focused on softwarized networks, performance analysis, and system modeling, with an emphasis on beyond 5G technologies.

Tutorial scope: This tutorial discussed key building blocks for setting up a private 5G testbed using Software-Defined Radios (SDRs), open source software components such as OpenAirInterface and srsRAN, and off-the-shelf modems / phones. Furthermore, case studies were covered highlighting research challenges as well as lessons learned in terms of measurement automation and reproducibility.

Slides: The slides of the tutorial [16] are available online: DOI: 10.25972/OPUS-42669.

Carmen Mas Machuca, Universität der Bundeswehr München): Resilience and Sovereignty Metrics and Models

Background: Carmen Mas Machuca is a Full professor at University of the Bundeswehr Munich (UniBw), heading the Chair of Communication Networks and Privat Dozent at the Technical University of Munich (TUM). Her research interests include techno-economic studies, resilient network planning, and optical networks. She's an editor for IEEE TNSM, OSA JOCN, and IEEE Communications Magazine.

Tutorial scope: This tutorial gave an overview of the different metrics that can be used to evaluate the sovereignty and resilience of a system. Existing models for these metrics were presented, as well as use cases where they have been applied. The minimum flow cut was discussed in the context of resilience modeling, which measures the smallest set of links or nodes whose removal most severely reduces network flow, making it a key indicator of a system's structural and functional robustness.

Slides: The slides of the tutorial [17] are available online: DOI: 10.25972/OPUS-42671.

V. SPEEDMENTORING

Following the very positive feedback from previous events, a speedmentoring session was organized for PhD students. This session provided a unique opportunity to engage directly with leading experts from both academia and industry. Participants were able to book short, focused meetings to discuss their research, recent developments in the field, or broader career-related questions. The invited keynote speakers from industry served as mentors, whose background was introduced in Section II. Amr Rizk and Guido Dietl, professors representing academia, also served as mentors. A short background is provided for completeness.

Fig. 4. Mentors for the speedmentoring session. From left to right: Amr Rizk, Johannes Riedl, Henning Sanneck, Tobias Hoßfeld, Guido Dietl, Rastin Pries.

Prof. Dr. Guido Dietl (University of Würzburg): Guido Dietl received his Dipl.-Ing. and Dr.-Ing. degrees (both *summa cum laude*) in Electrical Engineering and Information Technology from the Technical University of Munich. He has held various academic and research positions, including roles at Purdue University, the Australian National University, and DOCOMO Euro-Labs, where he focused on advanced wireless communication technologies. Since April 2022, he has been a Professor of Satellite Communication and Radar Systems at the University of Würzburg.

Prof. Dr. Amr Rizk (Leibniz University Hannover): Amr Rizk is Head of the Distributed Real-time Systems Lab at the Leibniz University Hannover. He is interested in performance evaluation of communication systems, stochastic models of networks and their applications to real-time systems. Before joining Leibniz University Hannover, he held professorships at Ulm University and the University of Duisburg–Essen and postdoctoral positions at TU Darmstadt, UMass Amherst and University of Warwick. He received the doctoral degree (Dr.-Ing.) with distinction from the Leibniz University Hannover in 2013. Among a number of awards he was a recipient of the Excellence in DASH Award at ACM MMSys'16 and the Best Paper Awards at ACM Middleware'17, MMSys'23, QCNC'24 and EMS'25.

VI. REVIEWER REFLECTION FORUM

This year's review process involved also experienced PhD Students as TPC members. The idea was to include them to gain experience with TPC reviews and learn from the process, while also benefiting from the fresh perspectives and up-to-date knowledge they bring through their active research. Their work often closely aligns with the topics of the submitted papers, making their contributions especially valuable. Each submitted paper was reviewed by three reviewers, including at least one senior expert in the field. And every paper was also evaluated by an experienced PhD student.

As instructions for the reviewers, the goal of the review process was formulated to provide constructive comments to the authors. In particular, to improve the presentation of their work, and hints for further extension of the topic. It was also asked to indicate the strengths of the paper. Guiding questions of the review process were as follows: What is the most significant strength of the paper? If the authors did one more (experiment/thing) what should it be? Is the problem formulation clearly described? Is the structure of the storyline easy to follow? Is the structure of the text and the presentation of the results clear? Is the research carried out thoroughly? Are the results and conclusions clearly described and reproducible? Are public data sets or open source code available? Are the discussions and conclusions detailed enough?

During the WueWoWAS'25 workshop, an interactive *reviewer reflection forum session* took place, which was open for all attendees, authors, and reviewers. The goal was to reflect about scientific review process from the perspective of an author and of a reviewer and getting familiar with community standards in the review process. An interactive questionnaire was used to trigger discussions, which was moderated by Tobias Hoßfeld and Viktoria Vomhoff. The responses and discourse demonstrated a consensus among the attendees. The following questions were asked and feedback was collected from the audience.

Author expectations: What is your expectation of a review? What do you appreciate? Overall, respondents emphasized the need for constructive, clear, and informed reviews that provide specific, actionable feedback rather than vague or superficial comments. They value objective, fact-based assessments from reviewers who understand the topic, offer helpful suggestions for improvement, and balance critical thinking with respect for the authors' efforts. Timeliness, fairness, and a genuine effort to improve the paper, rather than merely listing flaws or minor issues, were also seen as essential qualities of a good review. Respondents emphasized that reviews should be written by knowledgeable human experts, not generated by ChatGPT or other AI tools, providing superficial comments only. It is unacceptable for reviewers to urge or request authors to cite their own papers solely to increase personal citation counts. The primary focus must always be on improving the scientific quality or relevance of the work. Some quotes: "Facts – no opinions", "I see no weaknesses. Full Reject.", "No unreasonably large list of additional requests."

Review criteria: Which aspects to consider in a review? Respondents highlighted that a good paper should demonstrate

novelty, clear motivation, and a well-defined research gap, supported by sound methodology, reasonable assumptions, and transparent discussion of limitations. A strong paper also considers what it is not telling the reader by explicitly acknowledging limitations, assumptions, and open questions. This ensures transparency and scientific integrity. Respondents emphasized the importance of clarity, structure, and reproducibility, situating the work within the state of the art, and ensuring professional writing and critical reflection that go beyond merely presenting results. A key evaluation criterion is whether the paper addresses a genuine, relevant problem that meaningfully contributes to advancing research or practical applications.

Challenges for reviewers: What's the hardest part of being a reviewer? Respondents identified key challenges in reviewing, including limited time, lack of recognition, and difficulty ensuring fairness and accuracy when expertise is limited or papers are poorly written. They also noted struggles with self-doubt, time management, and maintaining professionalism, emphasizing the importance of providing constructive, well-understood, and fair feedback despite these constraints. The respondents emphasized the issue of papers repeating previously published claims without proper citation, underscoring the significance of acknowledging prior work to maintain scientific credibility and integrity. Some quotes by the audience: "Seeing that no changes were implemented after the paper was accepted.", "Motivate yourself, when the authors clearly spent no time on the paper in the first place.", "You get no recognition."

Reflection: What did you learn about reviewing? How might this review process help you improve your own work? Respondents noted that reviewing helps improve their own papers by offering insight into how others perceive clarity, structure, and communication, encouraging critical self-assessment and revealing unclear or overlooked aspects in their own writing, while also providing new perspectives on research presentation and evaluation. Some quotes: "if the reader is confused then it is not clear", "provides new ways of looking at the research", "WueWoWAS papers were better than the average conference paper. Reviewing them was more fun".

VII. THANKS

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- Infosim – a leader in automated network management solutions, providing cutting-edge software for monitoring, optimizing, and securing complex IT infrastructures.

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- the ORIGAMI project, which aims to redesign 6G architecture through global interoperability, zero-trust security, and integrated computing for sustainable, high-performance networks;
- the SUSTAINET-advance project, which aims to improve the sustainability and resilience of 6G networks from RAN to core.

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We will see you at the next edition of WueWoWAS in 2026.

Fig. 5. Looking forward to the next edition WueWoWAS'2026.

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